

Book Recommendation System using KNN Algorithm

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Abstract— In this paper, we present a book recommendation system that utilizes the KNN (K-Nearest Neighbor) algorithm. The goal of recommendation systems is to provide personalized suggestions to users, based on their preferences and their desired categories. Various techniques are introduced to recommend articles. Content, joint and related mining techniques are used. This approach helps reduce computational complexity and improve the accuracy of recommendations.

Keywords: Recommendation System, KNN Algorithm, Book categories.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommendation systems are used in hundreds of different industries from online shopping to music/movies and many services. Recommendation system are of two types collaborative filtering and content based filtering. In this recommendation system we are using content based filtering. Content-based filtering is one of the popular technique used in book recommendation systems. This approach is based on the idea of analyzing the content of a book, such as its genre/categories, author, language, and keywords, to determine its similarity to other books. There are several algorithms that can be used for recommendation Matrix factorization, Association rule mining, Deep learning in this system we uses KNN algorithm. The KNN (K-Nearest Neighbor) algorithm can be used to improve the performance of a book recommendation system based on content-based filtering. This algorithm works by identifying the k-nearest neighbors to a particular book, based on their similarity in terms of content. These neighbors are then used to make recommendations for new books to the user.

Challenges :

Data sparsity: In content-based filtering, there may be a large number of books with limited or no user ratings, which can lead to sparse data. This can make it difficult to identify the k- nearest neighbors to a particular book, which can affect the accuracy of the recommendations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Khalid Anwara.Et.al [1] executed "AI Procedures for Book Suggestion" (January 2019) in this paper they have utilized AI strategies which assist them with add their proposal framework

utilizing regulated learning and furthermore bunching techniques to bring the information. The program centers primarily around the dealers and internet business stage buyers developing incomes.

Satish Kolhe.Et.al[2] completed "request of library resources in recommender system using artificial intelligence techniques" (January 2018) in this structure they have used the set rule extraction method to do the substance based computation which describes the books into different classes and help the client with finding the books through the characterizations and another idea proposed by this system is the books to be placed in a decision tree plan so the clients can get the legitimate books, papers etc, this structure can be reached out by having a good informational collection and idea systems which lessen the hour of the clients to find books through the classifications .

Nursultan Kurmashov.Et.al [3] gave "Online Book Idea Structure" (February 2016) this system clearly shows that it is completed to examine the books essentially. The client is drawn nearer to fill the enlistment by adding his top picks and considering his/her top decisions the books are recommended to the user.is can be a fruitful way for endorsing the books to the client, on the other hand, the client can't find the best in class books of each and every class and need to search for various books which are dreary.

Vivek Kumar.Et.al[4]introduced a method for recommending books across different domains by utilizing tensor decomposition and semantic similarity techniques. This method involves extracting information from a secondary domain, which provides additional user preference data to improve the accuracy of recommendations in the target domain. The results of experiments demonstrate that this approach mitigates the problem of data sparsity and yields a higher hit ratio.

Nursultan Kurmashov et al. [5] presented a system designed for book reading. The system requires users to register and add their favorite books, which are then used to recommend similar books to the user. While this approach can be effective for personalized recommendations, it does not provide access to top-rated books in each category, forcing users to spend time searching for other books.

III. METHODOLOGY

A popular machine learning approach for classification and regression problems is called K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). The technique is predicated on the notion that in a multi-dimensional space, comparable objects have a tendency to cluster together. The KNN algorithm can be used in the context of book recommendation systems to suggest novels to readers based on how similar the books are to one another. The algorithm finds the K books that are closest to a specific book and then suggests novels that are similar to those neighbors. The KNN algorithm determines how similar two books are based on their attributes. Typically, a distance metric like Euclidean distance or cosine similarity is used to calculate the similarity. The method determines the K nearest neighbors of a particular book and suggests books that are comparable to those neighbors after calculating the similarity scores.

1. Data collection

Compile details about books, such as their authors, genres, descriptions, star ratings, and reviews. Online resources like Goodreads and Amazon can be used to gather this information.

2. Data pre-processing

Transform category variables into numerical variables, handle missing values, and remove duplicates from the data. One-hot encoding, for instance, can be used to encode different genres.

3. Similarity calculation

Work out the closeness between books in light of their highlights. One method for doing this is by utilizing cosine likeness. Cosine likeness estimates the cosine of the point between two vectors in a multi-faceted space. The nearer the point between two vectors is to 0 degrees, the higher their comparability.

4. Finding KNN

Based on the attributes of the KNN model created in step 5, identify the K closest neighbors of the user input book.

5. Recommendation

Provide the customer with recommendations for the books that are the most comparable based on their K nearest neighbors. The suggested books might be arranged according to their similarity score or weighted according to their level of popularity.

Activation Functions

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm is a nonparametric algorithm that does not involve an optimization or training process, so it does not use an activation function. However, if you're using a book recommendation machine learning model with activation functions, here are some common activation functions you can use.

A. Cosine similarity

This is a comparability measure regularly utilized in book proposal frameworks that utilization content-based separating. Cosine Similitude works out the cosine of the

point between two vectors in multi-faceted space, addressing how comparable the vectors are concerning bearing. In a book suggestion framework, cosine similitude can be utilized to gauge the likeness between the element vectors of his two books, for example, B. A progression of words in the depiction. The cosine similitude yield goes from - 1 (entirely unlike) 1 (completely comparable), with 0 demonstrating no connection.

B. Tanh function

The exaggerated digression capability (tanh) is another usually utilized enactment capability that maps any genuine number to a worth between - 1 and 1. It is much of the time utilized in brain networks since it can show nonlinear connections.

C. Sigmoid function

This is an activation function commonly used in machine learning models, including those used in book recommendation systems. The sigmoid function maps any real number to a value between 0 and 1. This is commonly used in binary classification problems where the output can be 0 or 1. Book recommendation systems can use sigmoid functions in neural network models involving collaborative filtering or hybrid filtering approaches. The output of the sigmoid function is interpreted as the predicted probability that a user will like a particular book.

D. Softmax function

This is the activation function commonly used in multiclass classification problems. Map the model's output to a probability distribution of the possible classes, such that all class probabilities sum to one.

E. ReLU function

The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function is a general activation function that sets all negative values to 0 and leaves positive values unchanged. It is often used in neural networks because it is simple and can speed up the training process.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

```
import csv
import numpy as np
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from flask import Flask, request, jsonify
```

This code imports three modules: csv, numpy, and flask.

The numpy module provides support for arrays and matrices in Python and mathematical functions for manipulating arrays and matrices.

The sklearn neighbors module provides implementations of various nearest neighbor algorithms, including the K nearest neighbors algorithm.

The Flask module is a micro web framework that allows you to build web applications in Python. This code is used to create a Flask application that can be used to expose the K-nearest neighbor classifier as a web API.

```
# Load the book data from a CSV file
with open('main_dataset.csv', newline='') as f:
    reader = csv.DictReader(f)
    books = [[row for row in reader]]
```

Reading the csv files.


```
# Create a dictionary to store books by category
books_by_category = {}
for book in books:
    if book['category'] not in books_by_category:
        books_by_category[book['category']] = []
    books_by_category[book['category']].append(book)
```

This code creates a dictionary to store the books by the categories given.

```
# Create a KNN model for each category
knn_models = {}
for category, category_books in books_by_category.items():
    X = np.array([[float(book['rating']) if 'rating' in book else 0,
                  len(book['author'].split(',')) for book in category_books])
    y = np.array([book['name'] for book in category_books])
    knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5, algorithm='auto')
    knn.fit(X, y)
    knn_models[category] = knn

# Initialize a Flask app
app = Flask(__name__)

# Define a route to handle book recommendation requests
@app.route('/recommend_books', methods=['POST'])
def recommend_books():
    category = request.form['category']

    # Find the 5 closest books in the same category
    knn = knn_models[category]
    category_books = books_by_category[category]
    X = np.array([[float(book['rating']) if 'rating' in book else 0,
                  len(book['author'].split(',')) for book in category_books])
    y = np.array([book['name'] for book in category_books])
    indices = knn.kneighbors(X)[1]
    similar_books = [category_books[i] for i in indices.flatten()[1:6]]

    # Return the recommended books
    return jsonify([{'title': book['name'], 'author': book['author'], 'image': book['image']} for book in similar_books])

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True)
```

Result executed, recommended the books based on the category.

V. CONCLUSION

This code defines a Flask application that exposes a book recommendation system. It defines a single route /recommend books that accepts POST requests and returns a list of recommended books based on the input provided.

The recommend books() function handles incoming requests to the /recommend books route. Extract the book category from the request form data and get a pretrained K nearest neighbor (ANN) model for that category. The book recommendation system works in conjunction with content-based filtering that recommends books based on similarity of characteristics such as rating and author name. The function then uses the KNN algorithm to find the 5 closest matches within the same category. The input characteristics for the ANN model are the book rating and author name length (separated by commas for multiple authors). This function returns a JSON response containing information about the recommended book, such as the book's title, author, and image.

The name == 'main' block is used to run the Flask application on the local server when running this script directly. The debug=True parameter enables debug mode. This is useful for debugging and development purposes. Overall, this code provides a simple implementation of a book recommendation system accessible via a web API. The recommendation system uses her KNN to find the most similar books based on user preferences. This comes in the form of book categories.

This paper discusses the application of KNN algorithm to recommend books based on the category. This book recommendation system that uses the KNN algorithm and content-based filtering is an effective way to recommend books based on a user's favorite book categories. A KNN algorithm is used to find the nearest neighbors of a particular book based on its features. The recommender system then returns a list of books that are most similar in characteristics to the input book. This approach lends itself to personalized book recommendations that take into account the user's preferences and interests. By analyzing the content features of books, such as genre, author, and keywords, KNN can identify similar books and make personalized recommendations to users. This approach can give more exact proposals than cooperative sifting techniques in situations where client information is meager or inaccessible.

The filtering approach that relies on content can be highly successful if a user's tastes are specific and there's plenty of data to assess pertinent book qualities. Specifically tailored suggestions can be made that align with a customer's inclinations, and modifications can be implemented over time based on how a user interacts with the system.

Improving user experience, the KNN algorithm with content-based filtering is a successful approach to book recommendation systems by recommending books based on users' favorite genres. Increasing interaction with book content, this method is efficient and effective for providing readers with their ideal book suggestions.

VII.REFERENCES

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